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NDRG2 gene copy number is not altered in colorectal carcinoma

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Supplementary material

Supplementary Table S1 Donor information

	Diagnostic	Age	Sex
Normal 1	Normal	87	M
Normal 2	Normal	72	F
Normal 3	Normal	30	M
Normal 4	Normal	21	M
Normal 5	Normal	41	M
Normal 6	Normal	25	M
Normal 7	Normal	23	M
Normal 8	Normal	34	M
CRC 1	Adenocarcinoma	67	M
CRC 2	Adenocarcinoma, Poorly Differentiated	53	M
CRC 3	Adenocarcinoma, (LM) Moderately Differentiated	75	M
CRC 4	Adenocarcinoma, (LM) Moderately Differentiated	56	M
CRC 5	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	62	F
CRC 6	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	61	M
CRC 7	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	77	F
CRC 8	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	46	F
CRC 9	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	46	M
CRC 10	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	81	M
CRC 11	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	57	M
CRC 12	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	68	M
CRC 13	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	57	M
CRC 14	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	41	M
CRC 15	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	62	M
CRC 16	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	62	F
CRC 17	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	60	M
CRC 18	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	64	M
CRC 19	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	74	M
CRC 20	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	68	M
CRC 21	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	73	M
CRC 22	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	75	F
CRC 23	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	70	M
CRC 24	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	61	M
CRC 25	Adenocarcinoma, Moderately Differentiated	60	F
CRC 26	Adenocarcinoma, Mucinous Poorly Differentiated	68	F
CRC 27	Adenocarcinoma, Mucinous Poorly Differentiated	63	F
CRC 28	Adenocarcinoma, Mucinous Moderately Differentiated	70	M

CRC 29	Adenocarcinoma, Tubular Moderately Differentiated	60	M
CRC 30	Adenocarcinoma, Ulcer Poorly Differentiated	79	F
CRC 31	Adenocarcinoma Ulcer, Moderately Differentiated	50	M
CRC 32	Adenocarcinoma Ulcer, Moderately Differentiated	71	F
CRC 33	Adenocarcinoma Ulcer, Moderately Differentiated	79	M
CRC 34	Adenocarcinoma Ulcer, Moderately Differentiated	40	M
CRC 35	Adenocarcinoma Ulcer, Moderately Differentiated	77	M
CRC 36	Adenocarcinoma, Ulcer Well Differentiated	47	M
CRC 37	Adenocarcinoma, Ulcer Well Differentiated	62	F
CRC 38	Adenocarcinoma, Ulcer Well Differentiated	48	M
CRC 39	Adenocarcinoma, Ulcer Well Differentiated	63	M
CRC 40	Adenocarcinoma (Fluffy), Well Differentiated	67	M

Donor information provided by BioChain Institute. M = male, F = female.

Supplementary Table S2 ddCt values and corresponding copy numbers for the *NDRG2* and *MYC* genes in colorectal tissue

Colorectal tissue	<i>NDRG2</i> – 5' end		<i>NDRG2</i> – 3' end		<i>MYC</i>	
	ddCt ± SD	Copy number	ddCt ± SD	Copy number	ddCt ± SD	Copy number
Normal 1	0.72 ± 0.40	loss	0.93 ± 0.38	2	1.02 ± 0.25	2
Normal 2	1.11 ± 0.44	2	0.96 ± 0.47	2	0.76 ± 0.56	2
Normal 3	0.96 ± 0.33	2	1.10 ± 0.44	2	0.76 ± 0.39	2
Normal 4	0.92 ± 0.25	2	0.80 ± 0.32	2	0.91 ± 0.52	2
Normal 5	0.94 ± 0.39	2	1.14 ± 0.30	2	0.86 ± 0.38	2
Normal 6	0.99 ± 0.32	2	0.99 ± 0.21	2	1.03 ± 0.34	2
Normal 7	1.15 ± 0.43	2	0.93 ± 0.27	2	1.06 ± 0.38	2
Normal 8	1.00 ± 0.39	2	0.83 ± 0.25	2	1.31 ± 0.48	gain
CRC 1	1.02 ± 0.00	2	0.86 ± 0.11	2	1.86 ± 0.85	gain
CRC 2	0.93 ± 0.08	2	1.11 ± 0.26	2	1.15 ± 0.27	2
CRC 3	1.24 ± 0.27	2	1.25 ± 0.04	gain	1.04 ± 0.14	2
CRC 4	1.35 ± 0.06	gain	1.25 ± 0.21	2	0.97 ± 0.15	2
CRC 5	1.27 ± 0.21	gain	1.23 ± 0.28	2	1.17 ± 0.00	2
CRC 6	1.15 ± 0.15	2	1.18 ± 0.18	2	1.41 ± 0.62	gain
CRC 7	1.09 ± 0.09	2	1.06 ± 0.13	2	0.91 ± 0.07	2
CRC 8	1.14 ± 0.27	2	1.10 ± 0.23	2	0.96 ± 0.03	2
CRC 9	0.87 ± 0.17	2	1.02 ± 0.11	2	0.95 ± 0.05	2
CRC 10	0.96 ± 0.32	2	0.96 ± 0.14	2	0.81 ± 0.19	2
CRC 11	1.20 ± 0.67	2	1.05 ± 0.17	2	1.71 ± 0.12	gain
CRC 12	1.43 ± 0.09	gain	1.37 ± 0.09	gain	1.29 ± 0.36	gain
CRC 13	1.13 ± 0.40	2	1.17 ± 0.13	2	0.91 ± 0.00	2
CRC 14	0.93 ± 0.26	2	0.86 ± 0.11	2	0.74 ± 0.05	loss
CRC 15	0.85 ± 0.35	2	0.81 ± 0.03	2	0.91 ± 0.02	2
CRC 16	1.03 ± 0.52	2	1.03 ± 0.04	2	1.05 ± 0.01	2
CRC 17	1.19 ± 0.14	2	0.82 ± 0.03	2	0.75 ± 0.30	2
CRC 18	0.95 ± 0.24	2	0.92 ± 0.02	2	0.83 ± 0.11	2
CRC 19	1.84 ± 0.50	gain	1.26 ± 0.06	gain	1.51 ± 0.40	gain
CRC 20	1.09 ± 0.41	2	0.78 ± 0.03	2	0.55 ± 0.15	loss
CRC 21	1.32 ± 0.42	gain	0.86 ± 0.28	2	0.99 ± 0.44	2
CRC 22	0.84 ± 0.01	2	0.70 ± 0.25	loss	1.12 ± 0.75	2
CRC 23	0.86 ± 0.22	2	0.82 ± 0.02	2	1.32 ± 0.88	gain
CRC 24	1.38 ± 0.42	gain	0.91 ± 0.03	2	1.61 ± 0.44	gain
CRC 25	0.85 ± 0.09	2	0.97 ± 0.19	2	1.84 ± 0.89	gain
CRC 26	1.50 ± 0.18	gain	1.16 ± 0.31	2	1.64 ± 1.01	gain
CRC 27	0.83 ± 0.41	2	1.00 ± 0.41	2	0.54 ± 0.15	loss

CRC 28	1.09 ± 0.09	2	0.91 ± 0.24	2	1.52 ± 0.10	gain
CRC 29	1.02 ± 0.11	2	1.07 ± 0.43	2	1.35 ± 0.47	gain
CRC 30	0.91 ± 0.42	2	1.25 ± 0.18	2	2.14 ± 0.75	gain
CRC 31	0.37 ± 0.02	loss	0.38 ± 0.07	loss	0.07 ± 0.02	loss
CRC 32	1.19 ± 0.36	2	0.79 ± 0.13	2	1.77 ± 0.32	gain
CRC 33	1.15 ± 0.11	2	0.84 ± 0.26	2	1.39 ± 0.02	gain
CRC 34	1.37 ± 0.31	gain	1.32 ± 0.05	gain	1.26 ± 0.14	gain
CRC 35	1.20 ± 0.06	2	0.94 ± 0.01	2	1.91 ± 0.11	gain
CRC 36	1.08 ± 0.35	2	1.49 ± 0.85	gain	1.00 ± 0.07	2
CRC 37	1.08 ± 0.01	2	1.56 ± 0.79	gain	1.33 ± 0.31	gain
CRC 38	0.69 ± 0.16	loss	0.94 ± 0.19	2	0.93 ± 0.02	2
CRC 39	1.09 ± 0.05	2	0.97 ± 0.06	2	0.78 ± 0.67	2
CRC 40	1.28 ± 0.44	gain	0.85 ± 0.02	2	1.07 ± 0.16	2

ddCt = delta delta Ct, SD = standard deviation

All samples were analysed in triplicate. Normal genomic DNA from blood lymphocytes was used as reference DNA and values were normalised to *GFAP*. Copy number loss is defined as ddCt < 0.75 and a gain is defined as ddCt > 1.25.